

Effectiveness of Contextualized E-Learning Materials to the Learners' Performance in Filipino

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Abstract:- Advanced digital competences, comprising the confident and critical use of ICT for work, leisure, and communication, are becoming increasingly important (Ala-Mutka et al., 2008). This study aimed to find out the effectiveness of contextualized e-learning materials on the learners' performance in Filipino at Datal Baca Elementary School, West Malungon District, Sarangani Division, Region XII, Philippines. Based on the results of the study, it was found out that teachers' selected teaching methods, techniques, and tools used in teaching are somewhat effective for learners. Meanwhile, the grade six pupils' performance in Filipino without the use of contextualized e-learning materials during the pre-test is 82.1% and 83.1% with the use of contextualized e-learning materials on the post-test. Muhammad Basri (2013) cited the same result in his study on "The Development of Contextual Learning Materials for English Speaking Skills. "He pointed out that the contextual learning materials with the criteria of the psychological, pedagogical, and methodological aspects were very valid (93.28%). As a result, the stages of instructional design are appropriate for producing contextual learning materials for English speaking skills. Finally, the results of this study also revealed that there is a significant difference between the two (2) variables in Filipino, where the mean of the pre-test result is 80.21 percent and 83.11% for the post-test results. The t-value for the two variables was -3.420, and the p-value was 0.001. The result implies that the results of the two variables have a significant difference; therefore, the contextualized e-learning materials are suitable for better learning.

Keywords: *Contextualization, E-Learning, Learners' Performance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

To fulfill the demands and expectations of contemporary digital culture, teaching strategies must be continuously modified and adjusted.

Contextualized training strives to impart fundamental knowledge for practical use. Although teaching fundamental skills is an essential first step in developing critical thinking about the subject matter, integrated education's primary objective is to teach the disciplinary content (Pearson, 2010).

According to Snyder (2002), contextualization is also a form of basic skills training that teaches reading and writing abilities against the backdrop of a particular subject, like philosophy.

Materials that help students process new information or knowledge such that it makes sense to them within their frames of reference are referred to as contextual learning materials.

By emphasizing tangible applications in a particular environment that is interesting to the student, contextualization is described as "a varied family of instructional strategies aimed to more smoothly link the learning of core skills and academic or occupational information" (Mazzeo, Rab, & Alssid, 2003).

The degree to which a skill is transferred will also differ depending on the type of skill being targeted, how the transfer is measured, the demands placed on the memory of the skill to be transferred, and the time interval between learning and transfer, according to Barnett and Ceci's (2002) theory.

Additionally, Caverly et al. (2004) investigated how first-semester students in developmental reading classes at a 4-year institution used a contextualized reading comprehension method. Chapters from textbooks used in core curriculum courses, which students had to pass to earn their degrees, served as the foundation for instruction. He discovered that statistically significant differences existed between students ($n = 56$) who participated in the contextualized reading course and those in a random sample ($n = 72$) who had the same reading proficiency on the pretest but did not get developmental instruction.

Advanced digital abilities, on the other hand, which include the confident and critical use of ICT for business, leisure, and communication, are becoming more and more crucial (Ala-Mutka et al., 2008). Teachers must have these digital skills to use social computing platforms in a way that helps their students and respects their privacy and safety (Bedecker, 2009).

The "media generation" should be the only term used to describe this generation, according to German Rolf Schulmeister (2006). He concludes that there is no brain rewiring, new thinking, or learning patterns based on secondary statistical analysis. Communication, setting up

dates, and preserving personal connections are just a few examples of scenarios in which media use is regularly incorporated.

On the other hand, according to Bessenyei (2007), connectivism views learning as a process in which the importance of informal information sharing, arranged into networks and assisted by technological resources, increases. Learning develops into a continuous, lifelong network of

activities that are integrated into other activities. If seeking and assessment transform into cooperative network, the motive for gathering and contextualizing knowledge grows stronger.

This was done to determine the impact contextualized e-learning resources had on the performance of Filipino learners at Datal Baca Elementary School, West Malungon District.

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

➤ Objectives:

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of contextualized e-learning materials on the learners' performance in Filipino at Datal Baca Elementary School. Specifically, the researcher sought answers to the following sub-problems:

- What are learners' perceptions about the effectiveness of selected teaching methods, techniques, and tools used by the teacher?
- What was the learners' performance level before using contextualized e-learning materials in Filipino?
- What is the learners' performance level after using contextualized e-learning materials in Filipino?
- Is there a significant difference in learners' performance levels before and after using contextualized e-learning materials?

The participants of this study were grade six (6) pupils, ten (10) boys and nine (9) girls, for a total of nineteen (19) pupils who were enrolled for the school year 2018-2019.

After the school head approved the letter request, the researcher solicited the cooperation of the learners' respondents, explained the direction in answering the questionnaire, and provided enough time to answer all the items.

Furthermore, the scores in Filipino subjects between pre and post-tests were collected and analyzed. This study used the descriptive comparative method of research. The checklist questionnaire on the learners' perceptions of the teachers' techniques and tools in teaching Filipino was used. The learner's pre-test and post-test results in Filipino were tallied and collected to determine the significant difference in the performance level of learners.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive causal-comparative design focused on learners' perceptions about the effectiveness of selected teaching methods, techniques, and tools used by the teachers and the level of learners' performance before and after using contextualized e-learning materials in Filipino.

A five-point Likert-type scale, a widely accepted technique for measurements of perception and effectiveness (Simonson, 1979), was used in the study, and the statistical procedures used for data analysis in the study included frequencies, percentages, analysis of variance, and the t-test. The.05 levels of significance were used for all statistical procedures and tests.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 Learners' Perception about the Effectiveness of Selected Teaching Methods, Techniques and Tools used by Teachers

Items	WM	Description
1. Demonstration	3.21	Somewhat Effective
2. Projects	3.00	Somewhat Effective
3. Lecture-discussion	3.00	Somewhat Effective
4. Chalk Board	2.16	Of Little Effective
5. Discussion	2.47	Of Little Effective
6. Role play	3.42	Somewhat Effective
7. Assignments (reading, written)	2.58	Somewhat Effective
8. Self-study	2.11	Of Little Effective
9. Computer-assisted instruction	3.63	Effective

10. Oral presentation	3.05	Somewhat Effective
Total	2.86	Somewhat Effective

N=19

The data in Table 1 shows that item number 4 got the weighted mean of **3.63** and was described as practical, while items numbers 6, 1, 10, 2, 3, and 7 got the weighted means of **3.42, 3.05, 3,** and **2.58**, respectively, and were described as *somewhat effective*. However, items numbers 5, 4, and 8 got the weighted means of **2.47, 2.16,** and **2.11**, described as slightly effective. **Overall**, the result got a weighted mean of **2.86**, described as **somewhat effective**.

The result implies that the teachers’ selected teaching methods, techniques, and tools used in teaching are **somewhat effective** for learners.

Table 2 Learners’ performance before the used of contextualized e-learning materials in Filipino

Interval	f	Percentage
96-100	0	0 %
91-95	0	0 %
86-90	0	0 %
81-85	7	37 %
75-80	12	63 %
74 and below	0	0 %

N=19

According to Table 2, 37% of sixth-grade students received an average of 81–85%, while 63% received an average of 75–80%.

Overall, the results revealed that the sixth-grade pupils’ performance in Filipino without contextualized e-learning materials is **82.1%**.

Table 3Learners’ performance after the used of contextualized e-learning materials in Filipino

Interval	f	Percentage
96-100	0	0 %
91-95	0	0 %
86-90	6	32 %
81-85	9	47 %
75-80	4	21 %
74 and below	0	0 %

N=19

The data in table 3 shows that 32 % of the grade six learners got average grades of 86-90 %, 47 % of the pupils got average grades of 81-85 %, and 21 % of the grade six pupils got average grades of 75-80 %.

Overall, the results revealed that the grade six pupils’ performance in Filipino with contextualized e-learning materials is 83.11 %. The result implies that contextualized e-learning materials significantly affect the learners’ performance in Filipino.

Table 4 Performance level of learners in the first and fourth grading results in Filipino

Variables	Mean	SD	t- value	p-value	Remarks
First Grading	80.21	2.097	-	0.001	With significant difference
Fourth Grading	83.11	3.035			
			3.420		

Table 4 shows the mean of the first grading result of **80.21** and **83.11** for the fourth grading result. The t-value for both variables was -3.420, and the p-value was 0.001.

The result implies that the pre-test and post-test results significantly differ and reveal that using contextualized e-learning materials in Filipino is effective.

IV. CONCLUSION

- *Considering the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:*
- Teachers' methods, techniques, and teaching tools are primarily effective for their learners.
 - Without using contextualized e-learning materials, the sixth-grade learners' performance in Filipino is 82.17 %.
 - The contextualized e-learning materials have a **significant effect** on the learners' performance in Filipino,
 - There is a big difference between the two variables, so contextualized e-learning materials are better for learning.

RECOMMENDATION

- *Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations made were:*
- A replication of the study should be conducted periodically to evaluate the use and effectiveness of selected teaching strategies used by teachers to address the needs of the learners.
 - This study employed descriptive research methodology, which might not produce all the related functions of the materials, to identify the changing perceptions of teaching and learning principles and strategies.
 - The validity and reliability of the components involved in selecting appropriate instructional learning materials should be tested in the study's model.
 - Conduct a study to determine learners' perceptions regarding the extent of use and effectiveness of selected teaching methods and tools because their perceptions may differ from others.

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